

Socioeconomic indicators and their impact on mental health: A data-driven approach using Python and R

Sahab Kausar¹, Naurin Naqvi¹, Shabab Akbar², Sapna Ratan Shah², Kashif Abbas³, Mudassir Alam^{4,*}, Nazura Usmani³

¹ Department of Statistics and Operations Research, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, India.

² School of Computational and Integrative Sciences, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, India.

³ Department of Zoology, Faculty of Life Sciences, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, India.

⁴ Indian Biological Sciences and Research Institute (IBRI), Noida, India.

*. **Corresponding author:** Mudassir Alam, Indian Biological Sciences and Research Institute (IBRI), Noida, India. Phone: +91-8171331795. Email: syedalamalig@gmail.com.

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Abstract

Background: Economic wealth is often thought to improve mental health; however, this relationship is complex and poorly understood. This study investigates how societal indices and economic variables influence mental health, challenging popular preconceptions.

Methods: Using advanced statistical tools in Python and R, we analyzed associations between mental health metrics and key societal indices, including Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Human Development Index (HDI), Global Health Security Index (GHSI), Climate Change Performance Index (CCPI), and Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI). Mental Health Quotient (MHQ) served as the primary outcome variable.

Results: Our data showed that GDP, HDI, GHSI, and CCPI all had negative relationships with mental health. Furthermore, positive relationships were found between MPI and MHQ, implying that economic distress is not always associated with poor mental health.

Conclusion: This study emphasizes the necessity of balanced societal advancement, which goes beyond economic and infrastructure growth. Social, economic, and environmental issues all influence mental health outcomes, necessitating a transformation in how societal development is assessed and sought.

Keywords: Human Development Index, Gross Domestic Product, Climate Change Performance Index, Global Health Security Index, Simple linear regression, Multiple linear regression, Mental Health Quotient

Introduction

Mental health is more than the absence of mental diseases; it is a condition of well-being that allows people to cope with life's stressors, find their own skills, and make significant contributions to their communities. The World Health Organization (WHO) emphasizes that mental well-being is more than only controlling active diseases; it also includes ongoing

treatment for happiness and general wellness. Globally, around 300 million people suffer from serious depressive disorders, accounting for approximately 4.4% of the global population (1). Similarly, a large number of people suffer from anxiety disorders, which are frequently accompanied with depression. The World Health Organization has classified depression as the main cause of disability worldwide, with anxiety placing sixth (2).

These situations strain healthcare systems, increase absenteeism, and reduce workplace productivity (known as presenteeism). The economic impact is tremendous, with depression and anxiety alone costing \$1 trillion each year and expected to reach \$16 trillion by 2030. In the United States, clinical depression has an economic penalty of about 1.6% of GDP (3).

Mental health difficulties are a prevalent public health concern and a leading cause of disability worldwide. According to the World Mental Health Survey, approximately 5% of people in 17 countries reported having at least one depressive episode in 2011(4). Alarmingly, more than 90% of those who commit suicide have previously been diagnosed with depression (5). Addressing mental health is critical for human well-being and societal benefit, necessitating focus and action on a personal, community, and global scale. Inferring demographic variables such as gender and age can help us stratify our understanding of mental health disorder epidemiology at the population level (6). Previous research have used electronic health records data to investigate gender differences in depressed behaviour from many perspectives, including prevalence, age of onset, comorbidity, and biological and psychosocial variables (7). For example, women are twice as likely as males to be diagnosed with depression, and a national psychiatric morbidity survey in the United Kingdom found that women have a higher risk of depression (8). On the other hand, men's suicide rates are three to five times higher than women's. Late-life depression has caused the suicide rate among those aged 80 to 84 to be more than twice that of the general population (9). Depression in the elderly is frequently associated with chronic medical disorders, which can increase the chance of death (10). As a result, using passively sensed social data to infer demographic information while investigating sad behavior can throw more light on depression epidemiology at the population level. One of the causes of mental health is the gender gap between men and women, as evidenced by differences in social, political, intellectual, cultural, and economic attainments or attitudes.

For example, Yazdavar and colleagues (2020) addressed the relevance of social media in mental health, demonstrating how multimodal mental health analysis can provide insights into public attitude and behavioral patterns (11). Similarly, Jones and colleagues (2010) investigated the influence of preventative programs on health-care utilization among kids with conduct problems, stressing the long-term impacts of early interventions on mental health outcomes (12). The COVID-19 epidemic increased mental health issues, as demonstrated by Saulle and colleagues (2022), who conducted a systematic analysis of the effects of school closures on children

and adolescents, highlighting the harmful repercussions of disturbed routines and social isolation (13).

In addition, mental health research has focused on health-related quality of life. Mrabet and colleagues (2004) compared the quality of life of people with epilepsy to that of the general population (14), and Michalos (2004) emphasized the larger implications of social indicators research for understanding health-related quality of life (15). The COVID-19 environment created additional issues for mental health, particularly among healthcare professionals (16), who looked into the constraints and job satisfaction of middle-aged and senior healthcare workers during the pandemic. Interventions designed to improve mental health have shown various degrees of efficacy. Meanwhile, another study looked at social representations of e-mental health among healthcare system actors, showing the changing attitudes toward digital mental health technologies (17). Research has also looked into the causes of positive mental health, including the links between self-esteem, character qualities, and social inclusion in adolescents (18).

The role of health systems in mental health outcomes has been critically evaluated, revealing possibly avoidable hospital admissions associated with secondary mental health care use (19). Several studies have examined the financial and societal ramifications of mental health. Allchin and colleagues (2020) looked into the use of the "Let's Talk About Children" intervention in adult mental health services, emphasizing the need of addressing intergenerational mental health concerns (20). Another study looked at how a history of poor mental health affects healthcare expenditures during the perinatal era, emphasizing the long-term financial burden of untreated mental health disorders (21). Furthermore, school-based mental health curricula have been shown to have an impact on peer violence and mental health outcomes (22), while another study focused on understanding teenage males' mental health and health-compromising behaviors in Sweden (23). The impact of mental health treatments in preventing suicide attempts was investigated (24), emphasizing the need of readily available mental health services. Environmental factors have also been associated with mental health outcomes. A study looked into the relationship between environmental exposures, health behaviour, and mental health (25), while Cai and colleagues (2020) did a cross-sectional study on mental health among healthcare professionals during the COVID-19 outbreak (26). Liljeholm and colleagues (2020)

looked into the impact of an integrated mental health and vocational intervention on young adults, emphasizing the importance of a comprehensive approach to mental health care (27). Finally, Mantell and colleagues (2020) investigated health literacy among adults with mental illnesses, finding the distinct obstacles this community faces in accessing and comprehending health information (28). In light of these different studies, the purpose of this research article is to integrate the available literature and provide a thorough analysis of the complex interactions between societal, economic, and environmental issues and mental health. By leveraging the findings from these studies, the paper hopes to contribute to the current discussion about mental health and inform the creation of more effective, focused interventions that address the unique requirements of various populations.

Materials and methods

Data under study

We have used secondary real data for analysis, drawing from several sources: the Report on Mental State of the World 2021 by Sapien Labs (29), the Global Gender Gap Report 2021 by the World Economic Forum (30), the Global Multidimensional Poverty Index 2021 by the United Nations Development Program and Oxford Poverty Human Development Initiative (31), the Human Development Report 2021/2022 by the United Nations Development Programme (32), and data on Gross Domestic Product. The study's goal was to determine the link between the Mental Health Quotient (MHQ) score and numerous social elements that influence it, as well as to investigate the relationship between the MHQ score and various socioeconomic determinants that affect mental health. MHQ was used to examine the population's mental health and well-being. It also helps identify at-risk individuals and subgroups and provides diagnosis-relevant information for ten illnesses.

The data is from 33 countries. The variables under study include:

- MHQ
- Economic Participation and opportunity (EPP)
- Education Attainment (EA)
- Political Empowerment (PE)
- Health and Survival (HS)
- Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI)
- GDP
- Human Development Index (HDI)
- Global Health Security Index (GHSI)
- Climate Change Performance Index (CCPI)

Correlation

Correlation analysis is the technique of determining the strength of the relationship between two variables. Correlation occurs when a change in one variable affects a change in another. The variables being investigated are MHQ Score, Economic Participation and Opportunity (EPP), Education Attainment, Political Empowerment, Health and Survival, Multidimensional Poverty Index, Gross Domestic Product, Human Development Index (HDI), Global Health Security Index (GHSI), and Climate Change Performance Index (CCPI). We utilized Python (3.0) and R. We also created a heatmap using the plotly.express package in Python 3.0.

$$\rho_{xy} = \text{Cov}(x,y) / \sigma_x \sigma_y$$

OR

$$r = \frac{n(\sum_{xy}) - (\sum_x)(\sum_y)}{\sqrt{[n\sum x^2 - (\sum_x)^2][n\sum y^2 - (\sum_y)^2]}}$$

n=Quantity of information

\sum_x =Total of all values for first variable

\sum_y =Total of all values for second variable

\sum_{xy} =Sum of product of first and second value

$\sum x^2$ =Sum of squares of the first value

$\sum y^2$ =Sum of squares of the second value

Simple linear regression

The simple linear regression model, which consists of a single regressor x and a straight line relationship with a response y. The simple linear regression model is

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X + e_i \quad i=1,2, \dots, n.$$

The dependent variable was MHQ, and the remaining factors serve as explanatory/independent variables.

Multiple linear regression

Multiple linear regressions are a type of regression model that uses a straight line to assess the relationship between a dependent variable and two or more independent variables. Multiple linear regression (MLR) is a statistical technique that employs multiple explanatory variables to forecast the outcome of a response variable. The generalized multiple two-variable regression function is:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1i} + \dots + \beta_n X_{ni} + e_i \quad i=1,2, \dots, n.$$

Where Y is the dependent variable, X1,X2,...Xn are the explanatory variables, ei is the error term.

Assumptions of linear regressions were:

- The regression model is linear in the parameters, though it may or may not be linear in the variables.
- X values should be independent of the error term.
- Zero mean value of error e, i.e. $E(e_i) = 0$.
- Homoscedasticity or constant variance of e. The variance of the error term is the same regardless of the value of X. Symbolically, $\text{var}(e_i) = \sigma^2$
- No autocorrelation between the errors. The observations are sampled independently. Symbolically, $\text{cov}(e_i, e_j) = 0$, if X is nonstochastic.

Normality assumption

The classical linear regression model assumes that each e_i is distribution normally with Mean: $E(e_i) = 0$

Variance: $E[e_i - E(e_i)]^2 = \sigma^2$

Cov(e_i, e_j): $E[e_i - E(e_i)][e_j - E(e_j)] = E(e_i, e_j) = 0$ $i \neq j$

The assumption given above can be more compactly stated as $e_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$

The dependent variable's normality was evaluated using the Q-Q plot, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, and the Anderson-Darling test.

Homoscedasticity

Homoscedasticity was evaluated to determine the error's consistency. The homoscedasticity was assessed using a fitted vs residual graphical evaluation and the Breusch-Pagan test.

Results

Exploratory data analysis

Venezuela had the highest MHQ (91) among the 33 countries, while the United Kingdom and South Africa had the lowest (46). The average MHQ was 68.5, with the first and third quartiles scoring 63.00 and 74.00, respectively. The median MHQ was 71, and Chile, Nigeria, Cameroon, and Mexico all scored 71. India's MHQ, at 56, was below average. New Zealand had the highest EPP score for girls (0.7630), while Iraq had the lowest (0.2280). The average score was 0.5999, with the quartiles being 0.5100, 0.6580, and 0.7090. India's EPP score was much lower than average, at 0.326.

Among 33 countries, Argentina, Belgium, France, Chile, Colombia, the United States, Canada, New Zealand, and Australia achieved the highest female Educational Attainment score of 1.00. The Democratic Republic of the Congo received the lowest score,

0.6580. The average score was 0.9518, with quartiles of 0.9660, 0.9920, and 1.000. India's score was higher than average, at 0.962. Venezuela has the highest female health and survival rate at 0.9800, while India has the lowest at 0.9370. The average score was 0.9680, with the quartiles being 0.9640, 0.9680, and 0.9730. New Zealand earned the greatest score for female political empowerment (0.6580), while Yemen had the lowest at 0.0010. The average score was 0.2864, with the quartiles being 0.1510, 0.2760, and 0.6300. India scored 0.276, which was below average.

Nigeria had the highest MPI (0.25400) among the 13 countries with accessible data, while Tunisia had the lowest (0.00300). The average MPI was 0.09431, with quartile values of 0.02000, 0.03300, and 0.13400. India's MPI was 0.123, which is above average. Among the 26 countries, the United States had the greatest GDP at \$22,996,100, while Ecuador had the lowest at \$106,166. The average GDP was \$1,750,866, with quartiles of \$315,006, \$466,136, and \$1,392,592. India's GDP was more than average at \$3,173,398 but lower than the median. Switzerland had the highest HDI (0.9620), while Yemen had the lowest (0.4550). The average HDI was 0.7756, with quartile values of 0.6860, 0.7580, and 0.9210. The HDI in India was 0.633, which was lower than the average. The United States had the highest GHSI of 75.90, while Yemen had the lowest at 16.10. The average score was 50.80, with the quartiles being 31.20, 50.80, and 58.80. India had a score of 42.8, which was below average. Among 19 countries with available data, the United Kingdom had the highest CCPI at 69.66, while the United States had the lowest at 19.75. The average CCPI was 47.14, with quartiles of 41.88, 46.13, and 57.59. India's CCPI was 63.98, substantially above the norm.

Continent-wise analysis

Plots are created using Python's Kernel Density (KD).

We collected data from 33 nations and separated them by continent to highlight their variability using the KD plot (Figures 1-10).

In addition, figure 11 depicts the previous 10 plots as a scatter plot matrix.

Interpretations from the Heat Map

Figure 12 shows a heat map of all the specified variables. A positive correlation of 0.13 suggests that as women's economic engagement improves, so does the MHQ Score.

A negative correlation of -0.079 indicates that as women's educational attainment grows, their MHQ Score drops. A positive association of 0.22 indicates that increases in women's health are connected with higher MHQ scores. A negative correlation of -0.13 implies that as women's political empowerment increases, the MHQ Score drops. A positive association of 0.085 indicates that when the poverty index grows, so does the MHQ Score. A negative correlation of -0.14 indicates that as GDP rises, the MHQ Score drops. A negative correlation of -0.11 suggests that higher HDI is related with lower MHQ scores. A negative correlation of -0.19 indicates that improved global health is associated with lower MHQ scores. A modest negative correlation of -0.008 indicates a minor negative impact on the MHQ Score.

Evaluation of normality

The histogram (Figure 13) shows that the MHQ approximates a normal distribution, implying that the normality criterion is generally met. At some points, the empirical density function deviates from the normal density function. The Q-Q plot (Figure 14) is used to further evaluate these variances.

From Kolmogorov-Smirnov-test, we have obtained p-value = 0.3503 > 0.05 = α . Hence, we fail to reject our null hypothesis i.e., MHQ follows Normal distribution. According to Anderson-Darling normality test, p-value = 0.09355 > 0.05 = α . Hence, we fail to reject our null hypothesis i.e., MHQ follows normal distribution

Simple linear regression model

The nine linear regression models are fitted using R software with MHQ as the dependent variable and each of the nine factors as the independent variable in each model.

Model 1:

Model 1 is between MHQ and EPP:

For linear regression model 1,

$$\text{Mental Health Quotient} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{EPP} + \epsilon$$

Before fitting the regression model, we check for homoscedasticity.

Test for Homoscedasticity

The Residual vs Fitted graph suggests the possibility of heteroscedasticity (Figure 15). To further analyze the heteroscedasticity, we employ the Breusch-Pagan test:

Breusch-Pagan test

From Studentized Breusch-Pagan test, we have obtained p-value = 0.1935 > 0.05 = α . Hence, we fail to reject our null hypothesis i.e., there is homoscedasticity which mean it has constant variance.

Simple linear regression

Fitting of Model 1:

Call: `lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Economic.Participation.and.opportunity, data = data)`
We get regression coefficients as $\beta_0 = 63.172$ and $\beta_1 = 8.957$.

Here, the intercept 63.172, indicating that when Economic Participation and Opportunity (EPP) is zero, the expected MHQ is 63.172. The slope β_1 is 8.957, meaning that for each unit increase in EPP, the MHQ increases by 8.957, demonstrating a positive correlation between EPP and MHQ. The Residual Standard Error (RSE) is 10.37, implying that the MHQ deviates from the true regression line by an average of 10.37 units. The Multiple R-Squared value is 0.01696, indicating that approximately 1.69% of the variance in MHQ can be explained by the EPP of females in a country.

Model 2:

Model 2 is between MHQ and Education Attainment:

For linear regression model 2,

$$\text{Mental Health Quotient} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Education Attainment} + \epsilon$$

Call: `lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Education.Attainment, data = data)`

Here, the intercept β_0 is 77.426, indicating that when Education Attainment is zero, the expected MHQ is 77.426. The slope β_1 is -9.331, meaning that for each unit increase in Education Attainment, the MHQ decreases by 9.331, indicating a negative correlation between Education Attainment and MHQ. The Residual Standard Error (RSE) is 10.43, suggesting that the MHQ deviates from the true regression line by an average of 10.43 units. The Multiple R-Squared value is 0.006317, indicating that approximately 0.63% of the variation in MHQ can be explained by the Education Attainment of females in a country.

Figure 1. The spread of the curves in the plot indicates that the variation in MHQ Scores is highest among European countries, followed by African and Asian countries. In contrast, Australia exhibits the lowest variation in MHQ Scores.

Figure 2. KD plot for economic participation and opportunity: From the spread of the curves in the above plot, we conclude that variation in EPP is highest in Asia whereas it is lowest in Australia. Therefore, Australia has lowest MHQ Score.

Figure 3. KD plot for health and survival: From the spread of the curves in the above plot, we conclude that variation in Health and Survival is highest in Asia whereas it is lowest in Australia.

Figure 4. KD plot for political empowerment: From the spread of the curves in the above plot, we conclude that variation in Political Empowerment is highest in Australia followed by North America and Asia whereas it is lowest in Europe.

Figure 5. KD plot for education attainment: From the spread of the curves in the above plot, we conclude that variation in Education Attainment is highest in Africa and Asia whereas it is lowest in Europe followed by Australia, South America and North America

Figure 6. KD plot for poverty index: From the spread of the curves in the above plot, we conclude that variation in Poverty Index is highest in Africa followed by North America and Asia while it is lowest in South America.

Figure 7. KD plot for gross domestic product: From the spread of the curves in the above plot, we conclude that variation in GDP is highest in North America whereas it is lowest in South America followed by Australia and it is moderate in Asia.

Figure 8. KD plot for HDI: The spread of the curves in the plot indicates that the variation in Human Development is highest in Asia, followed by North America, while it is lowest in Australia, followed by Europe.

Figure 9. KD plot for climate change performance index (CCPI): From the spread of the curves in the above plot, we conclude that variation in CCPI is highest in Asia whereas it is lowest in Africa and Europe.

Figure 10. KD plot for global health index: Based on the spread of the curves in the plot, we conclude that the variation in the Global Health Index is highest in North America, followed by Asia and South America, while it is lowest in Europe, followed by Australia.

Figure 11. Collective scatter plot for KD plot

Figure 12. Heat map of selected parameters under consideration

Figure 13. Normality analysis of the MHQ data using histogram

Figure 14. QQ-Plot shows that MHQ Score follows normality.

Testing for Homoscedasticity:

Figure 15. Residual vs fitted graph for homoscedasticity

Figure 16. The residual vs fitted model for homoscedasticity

Model 3:

Model 3 is between MHQ and Health and Survival:

For linear regression model,

$$\text{Mental Health Quotient} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ Health and Survival} + \epsilon$$

Call: lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Health.and.Survival, data = data)

For linear regression model,

$$\text{Mental Health Quotient} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ Health and Survival} + \epsilon$$

We get regression coefficients as $\beta_0 = -211.0$ and $\beta_1 = 288.7$

The regression analysis shows that the intercept is -211.0 and the slope is 288.7. This implies that for every unit increase in Health and Survival, the MHQ rises by 288.7. However, the link is inverse, implying that as a country's women's health and survival improves, the MHQ declines. The residual standard error is 10.2 with 31 degrees of freedom, and the multiple R-squared value is 0.04982. This suggests that, on average, the MHQ will differ by 10.2 from the real regression line, with women's health and survival accounting for 4.98% of the variance.

Model 4:

Model 4 is between MHQ and Political Empowerment:

For linear regression model,

$$\text{Mental Health Quotient} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ Political Empowerment} + \epsilon$$

Call: lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Political.Empowerment, data = data)

The regression analysis indicates that the intercept is 70.952 and the slope is -8.403. This means that for every unit rise in Political Empowerment, the MHQ drops by 8.403, indicating a negative association. In other words, when women's political empowerment improves in a country, the MHQ drops. The residual standard error is 10.37, with 31 degrees of freedom, and the multiple R-Squared value is 0.01765. This suggests that the MHQ deviates from the true regression line by 10.37 points on average, with Political Empowerment of Women accounting for 1.7% of the variance.

Model 5:

Model 5 is between MHQ and Multidimensional Poverty Index:

For linear regression model,

$$\text{Mental Health Quotient} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ Multi Dimensional Poverty Index} + \epsilon$$

Call: lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Poverty.Index, data = data)

The regression results show that the intercept is 70.076 and the slope is 1.639. This suggests that for each unit increase in the Multidimensional Poverty Index, the MHQ rises by 1.639, indicating a positive association. In other words, a country's MHQ rises in tandem with its Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI). The residual standard error is 7.41, with 11 degrees of freedom, and the multiple R-Squared value is 0.0004774. This means that the MHQ deviates from the real regression line by 7.41 points on average, with the Multidimensional Poverty Index accounting for only 0.04774% of the variance.

Model 6:

Model 6 is between MHQ and Gross Domestic Product:

For linear regression model,

$$\text{Mental Health Quotient} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ Gross Domestic Product} + \epsilon$$

Call: lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Gross.Domestic.Product, data = data)

The regression results show that the intercept is 67.44 and the slope is -3.148e-07. This shows that for every unit rise in GDP, the MHQ falls by 3.148e-07, indicating a negative association. In other words, when a country's GDP increases, its MHQ decreases. The residual standard error is 10.26, with 24 degrees of freedom, and the multiple R-squared value is 0.01891. This suggests that, on average, the MHQ deviates from the true regression line by 10.26, and the GDP explains 1.891% of the variance in MHQ.

Model 7:

Model 7 is between MHQ and HDI:

For linear regression model,

$$\text{Mental Health Quotient} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ Human Development} + \epsilon$$

Call: lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Human.Development, data = data)

The regression results show an intercept of 74.587 and a slope of -7.789. This means that for every unit rise in the HDI, the MHQ lowers by 7.789, demonstrating a negative connection. In other words, when a country's HDI increases, its MHQ decreases. The Residual Standard Error is 10.4 with 31 degrees of freedom, and the Multiple R-squared is 0.01309. This suggests that the MHQ deviates from the real regression line by 10.4 on average,

with the HDI accounting for 1.309% of the variance.

Model 8:

Model 8 is between MHQ and GHSI:

Call:

```
lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Global.Health.Index, data
```

For linear regression model:

$$\text{Mental Health Quotient} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ Global Health Index} + \epsilon$$

The regression analysis yielded an intercept of 74.167 and a slope of -0.121. This shows that for every unit rise in the GHSI, the MHQ drops by 0.121, indicating a negative association. Thus, when a country's GHSI increases, its MHQ decreases. The Residual Standard Error is 10.27, with 31 degrees of freedom, and the Multiple R-squared is 0.03752. This suggests that, on average, the MHQ deviates by 10.27 from the correct regression line, with the GHSI accounting for 3.752% of the variance.

Model 9:

Model 9 is between MHQ and CCPI:

Call: `lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Climate.Change.Performance.Index, data = data)`

For linear regression model,

$$\text{Mental Health Quotient} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ ClimateChange Performance Index} + \epsilon$$

The regression results reveal a slope of -0.006113 and an intercept of 65.656581. This means that for every unit rise in the CCPI, the MHQ drops by 0.006113, indicating a negative connection. As a country's CCPI increases, its MHQ tends to drop. The Multiple R-squared value is 7.074e-05, indicating that the CCPI can only explain 0.007074% of the variance in MHQ. The MHQ's average deviation from the real regression line is 11.24.

Multiple linear regression model

A multiple linear regression model was fitted using R software, with MHQ as the dependent variable and six independent variables: Education Attainment, Health and Survival, Political Empowerment, Global Health Index, and Human Development Index (HDI).

Mental Health Quotient (MHQ)

$$= \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{EPP} + \beta_2 \text{Education Attainment} + \beta_3 \text{Health and Survival} + \beta_4 \text{Political Empowerment} + \beta_5 \text{Global Health Index} + \beta_6 \text{Human Development}$$

For fitting of Multiple linear regression model, first we check for homoscedasticity and multicollinearity (figure 16).

Breusch-Pagan test

The studentized Breusch-Pagan test yielded a p-value of 0.121, which above the significance level of 0.05. As a result, we are unable to reject the null hypothesis and must infer that the regression model contains homoscedasticity.

Testing for Multicollinearity

The Variance Inflation Factors (VIFs) for our model vary from 1 to 5, showing modest correlation across the predictors. This amount of association is not significant enough to warrant corrective action. With this assumption satisfied, we may proceed to fit the Multiple Linear Regression Model.

```
Call: lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Economic.Participation.and.opportunity + Education.Attainment + Health.and.Survival + Political.Empowerment + Global.Health.Index + Human.Development, data = data)
```

Fitting of Multiple Linear Regression Model

For multiple linear regression model, we have obtained regression coefficients as $\beta_0 = 42.9908$, $\beta_1 = 38.1356$, $\beta_2 = 2.0117$, $\beta_3 = 9.0148$, $\beta_4 = -10.6671$, $\beta_5 = -0.4397$ and $\beta_6 = 20.007$ Residual Standard Error = 10.24 on 26 degrees of freedom Multiple R-Squared = 0.1975

As a result, the MHQ's average deviation from the correct regression line is 10.24, with the predictor variables accounting for 19.75% of the variance.

Discussion

The analysis demonstrates a complex link between the MHQ and a variety of socioeconomic factors. There is a positive association between MHQ and Economic Participation and Opportunity for Females, implying that more female workforce participation improves a country's mental health. In contrast, a negative association between MHQ and Education Attainment suggests that as the ratio of women to men in education grows, mental health may suffer, possibly due to stress and academic pressure. Health and survival correlate positively with MHQ, meaning that as the gender difference in healthy life expectancy closes, mental health improves. However, Political Empowerment is inversely connected with MHQ, implying that women's participation in high-level political positions may have a negative impact on a

country's mental health. Surprisingly, the MPI has a positive connection with MHQ, indicating that economic hardship does not always result in poorer mental health, as found in Nigeria. GDP, HDI, GHSI, and CCPI all have a negative correlation with MHQ. This suggests that higher GDP, HDI, and GHSI do not guarantee improved mental health, as shown by nations such as the United States and New Zealand, which have high economic and developmental indices but lower MHQ ratings.

Similarly, the United Kingdom's strong CCPI contrasts with its low MHQ, emphasizing the complex interplay of these elements.

We have found that a country's economic growth does not always translate into improved social and mental well-being in society. This conclusion contradicts the widely held idea that higher income leads to greater happiness. Our data reveals that both GDP and the HDI have a negative impact on mental health. Furthermore, while higher GHSI and CCPI values often reflect better economic situations, their negative connection with the MHQ lends credence to the idea that economic prosperity does not ensure good mental health. Interestingly, the MPI's favorable influence on MHQ implies that economic adversity does not always harm mental health. As a result, we conclude that a balanced approach to advancement is required, one that considers all of a country's positive requirements, in addition to the economy and infrastructure.

Conclusion

This study investigated the complex links between the Mental Health Quotient (MHQ) and a variety of socioeconomic characteristics across countries. Our data reveal some unexpected trends that call into question long-held notions regarding the relationship between economic progress and mental well-being. The findings suggest that female economic participation and opportunity, as well as health and survival indicators, have a favorable link with national mental health outcomes. Contrary to predictions, several classic metrics of national prosperity, such as GDP, HDI, GHSI, and CCPI, have negative associations with MHQ ratings. This pattern is especially noticeable in industrialized countries like the United States, New Zealand, and the United Kingdom, where strong economic and developmental indices are associated with lower MHQ ratings. Notably, the positive relationship between the Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) and MHQ implies that economic hardship does not always predict bad mental health results, as seen by Nigeria's case. Furthermore, our findings show that increased female presence in school and politics is associated with lower mental health scores, presumably

indicating underlying societal pressures and structural issues that require additional examination.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Appendix

The basic statistical constants are obtained using R software and are given below:

```
## Country MHQ.SCORE EPP
## Length:33 Min. :46.00 Min. :0.2280
## Class :character 1st Qu.:63.00 1st Qu.:0.5100
## Mode :character Median :71.00 Median :0.6580
## Mean :68.55 Mean :0.5999
## 3rd Qu.:74.00 3rd Qu.:0.7090
## Max. :91.00 Max. :0.7630
##
## Edu.Attnmnt Health&Survival Political.Empow Poverty.Index
## Min. :0.6580 Min. :0.9370 Min. :0.0010 Min.:0.00300
## 1st Qu.:0.9660 1st Qu.:0.9640 1st Qu.:0.1510 1st Qu.:0.02000
## Median :0.9920 Median :0.9680 Median :0.2760 Median :0.03300
## Mean :0.9518 Mean :0.9682 Mean :0.2864 Mean :0.09431
## 3rd Qu.:1.0000 3rd Qu.:0.9730 3rd Qu.:0.4190 3rd Qu.:0.13400
## Max. :1.0000 Max. :0.9800 Max. :0.6300 Max. :0.25400
## NA's :20
##
## Gross.Domestic.Product Human.Development Global.Health.Index
## Min. : 106166 Min. :0.4550 Min. :16.10
## 1st Qu.: 315006 1st Qu.:0.6860 1st Qu.:31.20
## Median : 466135 Median :0.7580 Median :50.80
## Mean : 1750866 Mean :0.7756 Mean :46.45
## 3rd Qu.: 1392592 3rd Qu.:0.9210 3rd Qu.:58.80
## Max. :22996100 Max. :0.9620 Max. :75.90
## NA's :7
##
## Climate.Change.Performance.Index Continent
## Min. :19.75 Length:33
## 1st Qu.:41.88 Class :character
## Median :46.13 Mode :character
## Mean :47.14
## 3rd Qu.:57.59
## Max. :69.66
## NA's :14
```

Anderson-Darling test

```
## Anderson-Darling normality test
## data: data$MHQ.SCORE
## A = 0.62741, p-value = 0.09355
```

Breusch-Pagan test

```
## studentized Breusch-Pagan test## data:
## fit1
## BP = 1.6905, df = 1, p-value = 0.1935
```

Simple linear regression

Model 1:

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Economic.Participation.and.opportunity, ## data = data)
##
## Residuals:
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
```

```
##      -23.586      -6.926      1.812      5.260      22.301
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      Std. Error      t value      Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)      63.172      7.566      8.349      1.98e-09 ***
## Economic.Participation.and.opportunity  8.957  12.249      0.731      0.47
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
## Residual standard error: 10.37 on 31 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared: 0.01696, Adjusted R-squared: -0.01475
## F-statistic: 0.5348 on 1 and 31 DF, p-value: 0.4701
```

Model 2:

```
## Call:
## lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Education.Attainment, data = data) ##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -22.151  -6.736  ##      1.832   5.811  22.886## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      Std. Error      t value      Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)      77.426      20.088      3.854      0.000547 ***
## Education.Attainment -9.331      21.020      -0.444      0.660188
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
## Residual standard error: 10.43 on 31 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared: 0.006317, Adjusted R-squared: -0.02574
## F-statistic: 0.1971 on 1 and 31 DF, p-value: 0.660
```

Model 3:

```
## Call:
## lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Health.and.Survival, data = data)
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -25.669  -5.493   1.064   5.507  19.043
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      Std. Error      t value      Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)     -211.0      219.2      -0.962      0.343
## Health.and.Survival  288.7      226.4      1.275      0.212
## Residual standard error: 10.2 on 31 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared: 0.04982, Adjusted R-squared: 0.01917
## F-statistic: 1.625 on 1 and 31 DF, p-value: 0.2118
```

Model 4:

```
## Call:
## lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Political.Empowerment, data = data)
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -21.4308  -6.6577   0.8632   5.7204  21.7204
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      Std. Error      t value      Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)      70.952      3.696      19.198      <2e-16 ***
## Political.Empowerment -8.403      11.261      -0.746      0.461
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
## Residual standard error: 10.37 on 31 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared: 0.01765, Adjusted R-squared: -0.01404
```

F-statistic: 0.5569 on 1 and 31 DF, p-value: 0.4611

Model 5:

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Poverty.Index, data = data) ##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -14.2778  -0.2958   0.5076   2.9188  11.7402
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      Std. Error  t value      Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)    70.076         2.961    23.665    8.73e-11 ***
## Poverty.Index    1.639         22.605     0.072     0.944
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***'  0.001 '**'  0.01 '*'  0.05 '.'  0.1 '.' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 7.41 on 11 degrees of freedom ## (20 observations deleted due to missingness)
## Multiple R-squared:  0.0004774, Adjusted R-squared:  -0.09039
## F-statistic: 0.005254 on 1 and 11 DF, p-value: 0.9435
```

Model 6:

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Gross.Domestic.Product, data = data) ##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -21.304  -8.095   2.734   6.570  18.013
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      Std. Error  t value      Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)  6.744e+01    2.170e+00    31.08    <2e-16 ***
## Gross.Domestic.Product-3.148e-07  4.630e-07    -0.68    0.503
## Signif. codes:  0 '***'  0.001 '**'  0.01 '*'  0.05 '.'  0.1 '.' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 10.26 on 24 degrees of freedom
## (7 observations deleted due to missingness)
## Multiple R-squared:  0.01891, Adjusted R-squared:  -0.02197
## F-statistic: 0.4625 on 1 and 24 DF, p-value: 0.503
```

Model 7:

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Human.Development, data = data)
## Residuals:
##      Min       Median       3Q      Max
## -23.0331  -7.0428   5.5092  21.7955
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      Std. Error  t value      Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)    74.587         9.596     7.773    9.04e-09 ***
## Human.Development -7.789         12.150    -0.641    0.526
## Signif. codes:  0 '***'  0.001 '**'  0.01 '*'  0.05 '.'  0.1 '.' 1
## Residual standard error: 10.4 on 31 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.01309, Adjusted R-squared:  -0.01875
```

Model 8:

```
## Call:
## lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Global.Health.Index, data = data)
## Residuals:
##   Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -22.625 -7.604  1.431   6.324  19.362
## Coefficients:
##               Estimate      Std. Error    t value    Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)    74.1675         5.4174      13.691    1.1e-14 ***
## Global.Health.Index-0.1210      0.1101      -1.099     0.28
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
## Residual standard error: 10.27 on 31 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared: 0.03752, Adjusted R-squared: 0.006472
## F-statistic: 1.208 on 1 and 31 DF, p-value: 0.2801
```

Model 9:

```
## Call:
## lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Climate.Change.Performance.Index, data = data) ##
## Residuals:
##   Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -19.375 -7.804  2.481   6.703  19.619
## Coefficients:
##               Estimate      Std. Error    t value    Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)    65.656581      8.699857      7.547     8e-07***
## Climate.Change.Performance.Index-0.006113    0.176284    -0.035     0.973
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
## Residual standard error: 11.24 on 17 degrees of freedom
## (14 observations deleted due to missingness)
## Multiple R-squared: 7.074e-05, Adjusted R-squared: -0.05875
## F-statistic: 0.001203 on 1 and 17 DF, p-value: 0.9727
```

Testing for Multicollinearity

Variance Inflation Factors (VIFs)			
Factor	Variable	VIF	1/VIF
1	Economic.Participation.and.opportunity	0.3446882	2.901173
2	Education.Attainment	0.3866133	2.586564
3	Health.and.Survival	0.6720344	1.488019
4	Political.Empowerment	0.4103390	2.437010
5	Global.Health.Index	0.2073789	4.822090
6	Human.Development	0.2060704	4.852710

Fitting of Multiple Linear Regression Model

```
## Call:
## lm(formula = MHQ.SCORE ~ Economic.Participation.and.opportunity +
## Education.Attainment + Health.and.Survival + Political.Empowerment +
## Global.Health.Index + Human.Development, data = data)
## Residuals:
##   Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -21.7755 -3.7336 -0.1393  6.2049  18.5564
## Coefficients:
##               Estimate      Std. Error    t value    Pr(>|t|)
```

```

##      (Intercept)          42.9908      267.6892      0.161      0.8736
##Economic.Participation.and.opportunity 38.1356 20.5825      1.853      0.0753
##      Education.Attainment    2.0117      33.1733      0.061      0.9521
##      Health.and.Survival      9.0148      277.1868     0.033      0.9743
##      Political.Empowerment -10.6671     17.3495     -0.615     0.5440
##      Global.Health.Index     -0.4397      0.2410     -1.824     0.0796
##      Human.Development      20.0070     26.3531      0.759     0.4546
##      Signif. codes:  0 '***'    0.001 '**'    0.01 '*'    0.05 '.'    0.1 '.'
##      Residual standard error: 10.24 on 26 degrees of freedom
##      Multiple R-squared:  0.1975, Adjusted R-squared:  0.01232
##      F-statistic: 1.067 on 6 and 26 DF, p-value: 0.4074

```